

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INDIVIDUAL ORIENTATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article explains the essence of information about individual educational technology, individual approach and thus the organization of the educational process, the possibilities of individual educational technology in improving the quality preschool of education.*

Keywords: *education, innovative education, individual education, technology, individual approach, quality education.*

Introduction: It is proving that the comprehensive development of society in the world is related to the content and quality of education. The task of education today is directly related to methodologically important problems of pedagogy, such as implementing the state policy set in the field, qualitatively fulfilling the state requirements for personnel training, creating a modern generation of educational literature, continuously improving the methodology of teachers-coaches, teaching students on the basis of personally oriented educational technologies. The solution of these problems ensures the qualitative fulfillment of the state requirements for the content of education, and leads to a positive solution of the main conceptual issues of education. These are processes related to scientific methodology and methodological research.

In today's pedagogy, organization of education on the basis of person-oriented, competence-based, heuristic technologies are considered as one of the effective forms of practical activity. These modern approaches are methodologically important content and form phenomena in pedagogy, they include comprehensive improvement of the student's personality, individual approach to them, increasing the practical value of theoretical knowledge, methods of forming certain competences in students, and a unique innovative approach to important issues related to the manifestation of their talents.

The continuous development of education takes place in the form of effective implementation of new pedagogical technologies used in the course of classes. The purpose of introducing new pedagogical technologies is to increase the efficiency of the educational process. Person-oriented educational technology consists in placing the pupil's personality in the center of the educational process, creating all the facilities and conditions necessary for the development of his abilities. In this technology, the learner appears as a subject of education with a wide range of opportunities. The attitude of the teacher to the student is considered as one of the main factors in the person-oriented educational technology. In designing this technology, it is important to take into account the mental, physical and age characteristics of the learner, his level of readiness for science.

Improving the quality and efficiency of education is considered as one of the main issues of pedagogy. The success of science approaches, technologies, methodologies, forms, and tools is ultimately judged by their contribution to improving the quality of education. Therefore, the quality of education is a fundamental and substantial research issue of pedagogy, and other components of education are considered as a means to it.

Approach processes related to stratification, specialization, property relations related to privatization are forming in today's education. In particular, this process is implemented in general primary education in the form of general education, specialized, creative and presidential preschools. Person-oriented, competence-based, heuristic and individual approaches can be cited as relatively new technological approaches in education. Researcher M. Qurbonova emphasizes that the technology of individual education serves to raise the dignity of the learner, to increase his self-confidence, interest in learning, and to form the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in everyday life.

In fact, the technology of individual education is considered as an approach aimed at creating convenient opportunities for the learner, the main goal of education is to ensure the harmonious development of the learner in all aspects. In individual education, the student's personality is placed at the center of the educational process, and all components of the educational process are directed to his education and training. In fact, since the primary goal of the educational process is to provide education, directing all opportunities and means to increase the personal and professional capabilities of the student, to bring his knowledge, skills and abilities to the level of competence, serves to increase the quality and efficiency of education.

In traditional education, a lot of attention was paid to other components of education, in particular, aspects such as strengthening teaching methods, improving tools, changing forms, improving technologies, adapting student and auxiliary literature to modern requirements. However, due to insufficient consideration of the requirements, needs, and opportunities of the learner, the above educational components could not show their effectiveness sufficiently. Individual education technology is important because it aims to eliminate this deficiency in the organization and management of the educational process. That is, the improvement of the tools could not fulfill its task sufficiently because the demands, needs, and inclinations of the learner, who should be served by those tools, were not sufficiently taken into account.

From this point of view, individual education technology is studied as one of the main strategic scientific research directions. According to him, the characteristics of the individual approach in pedagogical and psychological education are as follows:

- ensuring students' independence in the educational process, using teaching methods acceptable to them;

- confidence in students' existing knowledge, qualifications, skills and competences, experience;

- creating conditions for students to express themselves, taking into account their social status, lifestyle and opportunities;

- respecting students' mental state, emotions, and personal values;

- purposeful formation of learning skills specific to students' learning strategies;

- redistribution of professor-teacher and student tasks in the educational process: limiting the leadership role of the professor-teacher, treating him as an assistant, consultant.

Therefore, in individual education, the teaching process is organized based on the existing opportunities and potential of students, they are given maximum confidence. The purpose of didactic material used in classes based on individual education technology is to develop a curriculum, teach students the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities.

Types of didactic material in individual education technology include educational texts, task cards, didactic tests, etc. Tasks are developed by subject, complexity level, purpose of use,

multi-level, differentiated, individual approach, taking into account the leading type of student learning activity (cognitive, communicative, creative). At the heart of this approach is the ability to assess the level of achievement in mastering knowledge, skills, and competencies. The professor-teacher distributes cards among the students, finds out their cognitive characteristics and capabilities, not only determines the level of education, but also takes into account the personal characteristics of each student, creates the most suitable conditions for his development by choosing the forms and methods of activity.

It is advisable to choose teaching methods in accordance with educational technology and approach. Otherwise, the chosen method will not give the expected effect. In this regard, a set of methods suitable for individual education technology was determined in our research work. This is a growing-variable indicator, which is selected based on the individual pedagogical style of each professor.

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